

Impact of Various Aspects Of Socio-Economic Warp And Woof In Dairying Operations In Both Sectors I.E, Cooperative And Non-Cooperative In Western U.P.

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Abstract

Keeping in view the socio-economic fabric in western U.P this study was conducted in respect of Moradabad district of western U.P. and the yardsticks fixed for the purpose were size of operational holdings, family size, education status, composition of herd, species-wise average livestock per household and proportion of animals on milk as compared to milch animal and average milk yield also. The gist of the findings was that herd size increase with the size of land holdings, educational status promotes PCDF sector (Cooperative). Dairying as present is virtually dependent upon the species of buffaloes but species of crossbred Cow's needs to be promoted specifically under PCDF sectors. The supporting figures were average numbers of animals per household registered as buffaloes 4.44/4.20, local cow's 0.75/1.13 crossbred cow's 0.59/0.33 for both the sectors respectively. As far as proportion of animals in milk the figures reflected that 82.31%/77.27%, buffaloes, 83.78%/76.67% local cows and 87.50%/88.89% crossbred cows for PCDF (Cooperative) and Non PCDF sector (Non-cooperative) respectively. As far as yield is concerned the figures were 5.82 litre/4.97 litre for buffaloes, 3.36 litre/3.51 litre for local Cows, 9.23 litre/7.54 litre for both the sectors, respectively per milch animal per day. If we go for milking animals the yield values were registered as 7.07 litre/6.43 litre for buffaloes, 4.01 litre/4.55 litre for local Cows and 11.21 litre/9.89 litre for Crossbred cows under both the sectors respectively.

As far as category-wise trend in respect of yield per milch and milking animals concerned rising trend were registered in both the sectors in all the categories. Proportion of animals in milk as compared to milch animals was registered around 80 percent but our utter surprise in the case of the species of Crossbred Cow's the percentage was up to 100% at certain points of time. so this species is recommended to be promoted drastically under PCDF sectors. Overall findings were that at present dairying activities are concentrated mostly for the species of buffaloes.

Keywords

Soci-economic, Impact, Operational Holding, Warp And Woof, Milk Yield, Milch, Composition.

Introduction

As our country supports around 33% of total cattle inventory of the world in 2023 and ranks No-one in buffalo population in the world India has come out to be a hub for dairying activity as profession and source employment very extensively Dairying of course is standing as an industry in the present social-texture cooperative bodies and corporate body have surfaced and flourished over here for organized dairying. The net work of Corporative societies all over the country is the back bone of dairy industry and thus India has come out as the largest milk producers and consumers throughout the world. Indian dairy sector ofcourse has under gone massive changes after white revolution because of having tremendous potential, Dairy of farming is ancillary to agriculture growth and has registered a very major rule in uplifting the socio-economic status of rural household or investors. As a result the milk production has grown at a Compound annual rate of 6.2 to reach 209.96 million tonnes in 2020-21 from 146.31 million tonner 2014-15. The all India percapita availability of milk was reported as 444 gm per day on 2021-22. All these feathers in our Cap were studded due to dairy cooperative only in the shape of providing basic dairy services such as supply of Cattle feed, fodder, seeds, animal health services, artificial insemination, vaccination etc by professionally qualified managers. This socio-economic status of the farmers actually affects dairying management and breed selection

etc. High milk yield less expenditure of feed, breed suitable for an area, availability of government supported.

Aim of study

Commodity facilities are directly related to the viability of any unit In the above light this study was conducted and inferences were drawn after plotting the figure sector wise, species wise, season-wise and category-wise so that the inferences have universal acceptance as well as applicability.

Review of Literature

Resembling studies- **Mandi Kalyan et.al (2022)** The study Concluded that farmers participation in Cooperative dairying has a positive and statistically significant influence on socio-economics variable Members differed significantly from non-members in terms outcome variables, the mean difference value explained that the socio-economic conditions of members was better than non-members. The descriptive statistics for out come and explanatory variables as per the table given below.

Group	Mean value					
	Milk yield	Proportion of milk sold	Mean Education	Family size	Herd size	Milch animal
Members	11.59	1.42	8.61	7.45	13.27	5.56
Non-Members	8.81	1.19	4.64	6.42	6.24	2.94

The data present in above table showed that member group reaped higher milk yield as compared to non-member. This was due to cooperative member reared large herd sizes of milch animal comprising of high yielding crossbred cattle and buffalo.

Sharma Hemant et.al (2020)-The study confirmed that operational holding size of members households was 5.19 hect. as compared to non-member holding size being 4.17 hect.

Dubey L.R. et.al. (2014) - The study was performed in two blocks champawat district of Uttarakhnad state to compare the socio economies profile of members and non members. The findings were that average family size in case of member was 6.93 while in case of non members, it was 6.76. Education level Coefficient was registered as 5.60 in case of members while 4.76 in case of non-members. Average size milch animals was 1.16 in case of members while 1.03 in case of non member it was also observed that non-members do not go for crossbred Cows and buffaloes species instead they stick to Deshi cow breed only. Average milk yield in litres per annum was registered as 2481.33 litres in case of members while a meagre 1776.67 only in case of non member The inference drawn was that the awareness about the benefits from becoming members should be increased at large.

Niraula (2003) has also inferred that socio-economic impacts of dairy cooperatives is significantly positive, Cooperatives have ofcourse rendered the farmers more social and this changes them culturally as with good housing, hygienic toilets, bio plants. TV. Education etc.

Dhanapala (1988). The study inferred that dairy cooperatives have great importance as they play a useful role in promoting rural development especially they can facilitate the development of rural economics and thus it upgrade the standard of living.

Khan Nizamuddin (2014) - The study concluded that the importance of cooperatives due to fair returns and largest shares of traction through cooperative units. Another advantages that dairy cooperatives have emerged as a source of employment generation, efficient milk marketing and socio-economic development of dairy farmers so relevant policies and measures should be under taken to ensure efficient milk marketing better remuneration and sustainable socio-economic development of entrepreneur.

Priscill Laishram and chauhan A.K. (2019) The study inferred that About 11 percent of heads of household amongst members cooperatives were illiterate as compared to 15% amongst non-member co-operatives. A majority of household from members cooperative (32.50%) and non member Cooperative (27.50%) had attained middle level schooling. The average land holding size was found higher in case of cooperative member (0.66 acres) compared to that of non-cooperative member Another findings shows that ratio of crossbred to total milch cow's was higher for member cooperative (0.691) as compared to that of non member respondents (0.361) with significant difference.

Methodology

Primary data were collected 240 milk producing households from different villages of Moradabad district of western U.P covering all the thesils and all the blocks so that the data represents the households of different size of land holding, educational status and financial back ground so that genuine research work be accomplished and help the potential investors to plan further investment strategies Moradabad district of western U.P. was purposely selected for this study as it possesses not only a developed crop culture but also a greater milk potentiality for reaching comprehensive analysis. This district occupies prominent place in the state on account of its livestock wealth. The first milk product factory of PCDF was established in May 1970, in Moradabad district which recorded appreciable growth shortly. In the study area village. level cooperative societies were developed by PCDF on Anand Patteren. The district is endowed with fertile soil and a excellent irrigation facilities favourable for high intensity of crops. keeping in new the study area was chosen.

Sampling

The data so collected was bifurcate on the basis of PCDF and Non PCDF sectors and different categories were assigned on the basis of size of land holding as portable being given here under.

S.No.	Category	Size of land holdings (in hectares)
1	Landless Labourer Producers	NIL
2	Marginal Farmers	Up to 1.00
3	Small Farmers	1.00-2.00
4	Medium Farmers	2.00-4.00
5	Large Farmers	Above 4.00

The sample was pre determined for 120 household from PCDF sector and 120 households from non PCDF sectors for the analysis a seasonal impact, the data were collected thrice in all the three seasons namely from March to June (summer), July to October (rainy season), and November to February (winter season) standard Adults Units (SAU'S) were calculated as per the scale being mentioned here under. (Singh.K. 1984)

Buffalo in milk = 1 unit

Buffalo dry =0.4 unit

Local cow in milk = 0.7 unit

Local cow dry = 0.3 unit

Crossbred cow in milk = 1.4 unit

Crossbred Cow dry = 1.0 unit

Heifer = 0.5 unit

Young stock = 0.2 unit

(Male & Female)

Draught dairy animal = 0.5 Unit

The weight assigned for the conversion of female labour and child labour into main equivalent were as under.

2 Males = 3 Females

1 Male = 1.5 Female

1 male = 2 children

Result and Discussion

This study was conducted to analysis socio-economic profile of the households resorting to dairying under PCDF and Non PCDF sectors and important inferences were drawn regarding socio-economic texture of the Covered household on the basis of under mentioned broader heads.

1. Size of operational holdings.
2. Family size and its composition.
3. Educational status.
4. Composition of herd strength.
5. Species wise average number of animal per household.
6. Proportion of animals in milk as compared to milch animal.
7. Average milk yield per milch/milking animal.

Figure were collected under above mentioned heads in respect of both the sectors just to analysis impact of cooperative activities and community facilities over unorganized i.e, non-cooperative members The findings were eye opener as under.

Size of operation holdings

Land owners respondents were categorized in four categories as per the standards fixed by NCA (1976) Average land holding size sectors wise was found as depicted in the following table-1 enclosed.

Distribution of sample households according to their operational lands (In hectares) Table No.1

Household Category	Average size of operational land holding (In hectares)
Under PCDF (Beneficiary)	
Marginal farmers	0.556
Small Farmers	1.667
Medium Farmers	3.113
Large Farmers	5.231
All farmers	1.749
Under Non PCDF (Non Beneficiary)	
Marginal Farmers	0.537
Small Farmers	1.541
Medium Farmers	2.529
Large Farmers	5.180
All Farmers	1.650

We observed that the average size of operational land-holding in both the sectors was small farmers 0.556 hecture/0.537hect, marginal farmers 1.667 hect/1.541hec, Medium farmers 3.113 hect 2.529 hect, Large farmers 5.231hect/5.180hect for PCDF and Non PCDF sectors respectively. Overall average for all the households covered was 1.749 hect. in case of PCDF while 1.650 in case of Non-PCDF sectors. The analysis proved that size of average holding under PCDF scoter were bigger than the average size under non-PCDF sectors. Thus the analysis revealed that the bigger the holding the higher is the preference to opt PCDF sectors.

Table-2 Family composition of milk producers according to sex-age

Simple household category	No. of Household	Male				Female				Overall			No. of females per thousand Males
		Less than 5 Yrs	5-18 Yrs	18 & Above Yrs	Total	Less than 5 Yrs	5-18 Yrs	18 & Above Yrs	Total	Average Family size	Sex Ratio		
											Male	Female	
Under PCDF (Beneficiary)													
Landless L	17	0.59	0.88	2.18	3.65	0.76	0.88	1.59	3.23	6.88	53.00	47.00	887
Marginal F	53	0.28	1.30	1.64	3.22	0.26	1.08	1.34	2.68	5.91	54.63	45.37	830
Small F	21	0.48	0.86	2.47	3.81	0.38	1.14	1.91	3.43	7.24	52.63	47.37	900
Medium F	17	0.65	1.47	2.47	4.59	0.35	1.00	2.24	3.59	8.18	56.12	43.88	782
Large F	12	0.84	1.08	3.00	4.92	0.25	1.00	2.75	4.00	8.92	55.14	44.86	814
All	120	0.47	1.17	2.11	3.75	0.37	1.04	1.74	3.15	6.90	54.35	45.65	840
Under PCDF (Non-Beneficiary)													
Landless L	20	0.35	1.15	2.35	3.85	0.40	0.80	1.75	2.95	6.80	56.82	43.38	766
Marginal F	52	0.46	1.19	1.71	3.36	0.19	0.87	1.35	2.41	5.77	58.33	41.67	714
Small F	19	0.32	1.26	1.95	3.53	0.21	1.26	1.63	3.10	6.63	53.17	46.83	881
Medium F	16	0.94	0.75	2.25	3.94	0.19	1.31	2.12	3.62	7.56	52.07	47.93	921
Large F	13	0.46	1.54	2.69	4.69	0.46	1.39	2.69	4.54	9.23	50.83	49.17	967
All	120	0.48	1.18	2.03	3.69	0.26	1.03	1.71	3.00	6.69	55.17	44.83	813

Table-3 Education status of head of the sample households (in percentage)

Sample Household Category	No of household	Education Status						
		Illiterate	Primary	Middle	High School	Intermediate	Graduate	Above Graduate
Under PCDF (Beneficiary)								
Landless L	17	76.48	5.88	5.88	5.88	5.88	-	-
Marginal F	53	43.40	24.52	15.09	7.55	7.55	1.89	-
Small F	21	23.81	19.05	23.81	19.05	9.52	4.76	-
Medium F	17	17.65	11.76	11.76	23.53	17.65	11.76	5.89
Large F	12	8.33	8.33	8.33	25.00	25.00	16.68	8.33
All	120	37.50	17.50	14.17	13.33	10.83	5.00	1.67
Under Non-PCDF (Non-Beneficiary)								
Landless Laborers	20	80.00	10.00	5.00	5.00	-	-	-
Marginal F	52	65.38	11.54	7.69	9.62	5.77	-	-
Small F	19	57.89	15.79	10.53	10.53	-	5.26	-
Medium Farmer	16	50.00	18.75	12.50	12.50	-	6.25	-
Large F	13	38.46	23.08	15.39	15.38	7.69	-	-
All	120	61.67	14.17	9.16	10.00	3.33	1.67	-

